

REVIEW

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The use of web resources for metabolomics in horticultural crops

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Abstract

Metabolomics, a rapidly evolving field, has revolutionized horticultural crop research by enabling comprehensive analysis of metabolites that influence plant yield, growth, quality and nutritional value. The integration of web-based resources, including databases, computational tools and analytical platforms has significantly enhanced metabolomics studies by facilitating data processing, metabolite identification and pathway analysis. Moreover, the application of machine learning algorithms to these web resources has further optimized data interpretation, enabling more accurate prediction of metabolic profiles. Publicly available reference libraries and bioinformatic tools support precision of breeding, postharvest quality assessment and ultimately improving crop yield and sustainability. In this mini-review, we explore the current status of the diverse range of plant metabolomics databases in horticultural crops, highlighting the synergy between machine learning and traditional bioinformatics methods, their applications, challenges and future prospects in advancing plant science and agricultural innovation.

Keywords Metabolite databases, Bioinformatic tools, Plant metabolomics and horticultural crops

Introduction

Metabolomics emerged at the end of the last century, with the term coined by analogy with genomics and transcriptomics to refer to the metabolite complement of the cell in a review of Stephen Oliver (Oliver et al. 1998). However, arguably the paper by Fiehn and co-workers published in (2000) wherein gas chromatography (GC) coupled to mass spectrometry (MS) defined the chemical composition of a morphological and metabolic mutant of the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*, and describing the changes in the level of 326 analytes, is a more memorable landmark. This work thus greatly extended the early metabolite profiling study of Sauter et al (Sauter et al. 1991), which presented the technology as a means of putative classification of the mode-of-action of pesticides. Thus the advent of metabolomics in plants arguably preceded that in microbes and mammals although

the approach was also rapidly adopted in these communities (Aharoni et al. 2023; Giera et al. 2022). During the next two decades, metabolomics had the considerable advantage over profiling technologies such as transcriptomics and proteomics in that it is not directly reliant on the genome sequence. In this period the species scope of metabolomics rapidly expanded, such that it was no longer merely a tool for identifying biomarkers of cellular circumstance but additionally a cornerstone of systems biology and an approach that could provide mechanistic insight into metabolic regulation (Fernie and Schauer 2009; Meyer et al. 2007). This advantage has subsequently disappeared following the widespread adoption of next-generation sequencing, and the lack of linear relationship between the genome and the metabolome now represents part of the problem in identification of unknown analytes (Fernie and Stitt 2012). However, it does mean that metabolomics resources are available for a very wide range of species (~ 500) including a large number of horticultural crops (such as tomatoes, cucumber, strawberry and pepper). Previous reviews have addressed resources available for metabolomics in general (Perez de Souza

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and Fernie 2024) as well as plant metabolomics more specifically (Perez de Souza et al. 2017; Tohge and Fernie 2009). However, given the sheer number of publications that have been published over the last quarter of a century, we feel that the time is ripe for a focused review only on metabolomics of horticultural crops.

Such resources are particularly important in plants given that whilst the size of the metabolome for prokaryotes has been estimated at a couple of thousand, that of the plant kingdom dwarves these numbers, with estimates ranging between 200 000 and 1 million metabolites (Shen et al. 2023). Over the last two decades, metabolomics has been utilized to address a wide range of important questions in plant biology, including pathway structure (Shen et al. 2023), the influence of metabolism on growth (Meyer et al. 2007; Sulpice et al. 2009), plant ecology (Davey et al. 2008), various aspects of plant genetics including evolution and the domestication syndrome (Alseekh et al. 2021; Beleggia et al. 2016; Kliebenstein 2009) and detailed characterizations of the metabolic response to biotic and abiotic stressors. In the following review, we will discuss several issues the first being the availability of tools for chromatography since we last reviewed this in Perez de Souza and Fernie (2024), the number of resources has massively increased. Thus, we will update our overview of the most useful tools. Secondly, we will review the current status of the board variety of plant metabolomics databases. In this respect, we list sources of archived data and their respective volumes of data. We also briefly discuss recent meta-analyses, there is great potential for cross-study comparisons on metabolite responses in determining common responses between either genetic or environmental perturbations of metabolism. Finally, we will provide an outlook as to the horticulturally important questions that we will ultimately be able to address *via* the assembly of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)-minded database assemblies.

Overview of metabolomics and key web-based databases for horticultural plant research

The main goal of metabolomics is to unravel the intricate metabolic pathways and networks that coordinate diverse biological functions within organisms. Despite nearly two decades of untargeted metabolomics studies on various plant parts and growth conditions, a complete understanding of plant metabolomes remains elusive. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is widely used due to its high sensitivity and broad metabolite coverage (Theodoridis et al. 2012). However, a major challenge in metabolomics is the shortage of chemical standards, which limits the accurate identification of many detected metabolites. In horticultural plants, this

challenge is particularly significant, as precise metabolite identification is crucial for understanding traits related to flavor, nutrition, stress resistance and post-harvest quality.

Databases provide researchers with valuable resources to analyze and interpret metabolomics data fostering collaboration and accelerating discoveries in plant science. A wide range of metabolomics databases exist, each providing unique formation, from mass spectrometry spectra to metabolic pathways. These databases enable researchers to identify unknown metabolites, compare metabolic profiles across species and integrate data with omics approaches for a comprehensive understanding of plant metabolism. As metabolomics research has advanced, both databases and analytical tools have been continuously updated to incorporate the latest discoveries. To fully employ these resources, metabolomics software should be capable of (i) processing raw spectral data, (ii) statistical analysis of significantly expressed metabolites, (iii) integration with metabolite databases for accurate identification, (iv) multi-omics data integration and analysis and (v) bioinformatics analysis with advanced visualization of molecular interaction networks (Fig. 1).

Several metabolomics databases have been developed to support horticultural plants, providing essential resources for studying metabolism in fruits, vegetables and ornamental species. Databases such as the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) (Kanehisa and Goto 2000) and KNApSACk (Afendi et al. 2012) contain information on plant metabolites, including those from horticultural crops. The Plant Metabolic Network (PMN) (Schlöpfer et al. 2017) hosts species-specific pathway databases, such as SolCyc for tomato and OryzaCyc for rice, aiding in the exploration of metabolic pathways relevant to crop quality and stress responses. By using these databases, researchers gain deeper insights into the metabolic diversity of horticultural plants. Building on these existing resources, we will next introduce some of the novel horticultural metabolomics databases that further enhance research by providing comprehensive metabolic profiles, species-specific datasets and advanced analytical tools tailored for horticultural crops. To enhance clarity and utility for researchers, we categorized over 30 metabolomics databases relevant to horticultural crops into four main groups based on analytical methodology, species focus, metabolite type and functional application. These categories include: (i) Methodology-Based Databases, (ii) Species-Specific and Crop-Focused Databases, (iii) Databases Emphasizing Secondary Metabolites and Natural Products and (iv) Meta-Analysis and Data Integration Tools. A summary of these databases, along with their respective links, is provided in Table 1 for easy reference.

Fig. 1 A comprehensive workflow of metabolomics sample preparation to data processing, illustrating key steps from sample preparation and analytical techniques (e.g., LC-MS, GC-MS) to data processing, statistical analysis, and metabolite identification using online databases. The figure highlights the integration of computational tools for peak detection, annotation, and pathway analysis, providing a systematic approach to metabolomics research

Table 1 The recent metabolomics databases

Metabolomics databases	References	Link	Methodology	Species Scope
<i>LC-MS/GC-MS Centric Databases</i>				
METASPACE-ML	(Wadie et al. 2024)	https://apps.embl.de/metaspacexontext/	LC-MS	Multi-species
MetFrag	(Ruttkies et al. 2016)	https://msbi.ipb-halle.de/MetFrag/	LC-MS/MS	Multi-species
LIPID MAPS	(Conroy et al. 2024)	www.lipidmaps.org	LC-MS, GC-MS	Multi-species
LipidSig 2.0	(Liu et al. 2024)	https://lipidsig.bioinfomics.org/	LC-MS	Multi-species
LipidSuite	(Mohamed and Hill 2021)	http://suite.lipidr.org	LC-MS	Multi-species
COCONUT	(Sorokina et al. 2021)	https://coconut.naturalproducts.net	LC-MS	Multi-species
PathBank 2.0	(Wishart et al. 2024)	https://pathbank.org/	Pathway integration	Multi-species
SCIPDb	(Priya et al. 2023)	http://223.31.159.3/plant_compl ete/index_orangesunset.php	LC-MS	Multi-species
<i>Multi-Platform Databases (LC-MS, NMR)</i>				
Metabolights	(Yurekten et al. 2024)	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/	LC-MS, GC-MS, NMR	Multi-species
PaintOmics 4	(Liu et al. 2022)	https://paintomics.org/	Multi-omics	Multi-species
RefMetaPlant	(Shi et al. 2024a)	https://www.biosino.org/RefMetaDB/	LC-MS, NMR	Multi-species
OmicsSuite	(Miao et al. 2023)	https://omicssuite.github.io/#/	Multi-omics	Multi-species
ModelSEED	(Seaver et al. 2021)	https://modelseed.org/biochem	Genome-scale modelling	Multi-species
<i>Horticultural Crop-Specific Databases</i>				
TOMATOMET	(Ara et al. 2021)	https://metabolites.in/tomato-fruits/	LC-MS, GC-MS	Tomato
PMhub 1.0	(Tian et al. 2024)	https://pmhub.org.cn/#/	LC-MS	Multi-species
MMHub	(Li et al. 2020)	https://biodb.swu.edu.cn/mmdb/	LC-MS	Mullberry
ArecaceaeMDB	(Yang et al. 2023a)	http://arecaceae-gdb.com/#/	LC-MS	Arecaceae (Palms)
LettuceGDB	(Guo et al. 2023)	https://www.lettucegdb.com/	LC-MS	Lettuce
BoGDB	(Wang et al. 2022)	http://www.bogdb.com/	LC-MS	Brassica oleracea
BnIR	(Yang et al. 2023b)	http://yanglab.hzau.edu.cn/BnIR	LC-MS	Brassica napus
PlantMetSuite	(Liu et al. 2023)	https://plantmetsuite.verysgenome.com/	LC-MS	Multi-species
Corriander Genomics Database	(Song et al. 2020)	http://cgdb.bio2db.com/	LC-MS	Corriander and carrot
Metabolite Database for RTB	(Price et al. 2020)	(Supplementary files of the original article)	LC-MS, GC-MS	Banana, cassava, potato, sweet potato, yam
<i>Broad-Spectrum Plant Metabolomics Databases</i>				
Plant Reactome Knowledgebase	(Gupta et al. 2024)	https://plantreactome.gramene.org	Pathway-based	Multi-species
PMN 16	(Hawkins et al. 2025)	https://plantcyc.org/	Pathway-based	Multi-species
MetaCyc	(Caspi et al. 2020)	https://metacyc.org/	Pathway-based	Multi-species
CropMetabolome	(Shi et al. 2024b)	http://www.cropmetabolome.com/	LC-MS, GC-MS	Multiple Crops
Metadb	(Gao et al. 2024)	http://medmetadb.ynau.edu.cn	LC-MS	Multi-species
HypoRiPPAtlas	(Lee et al. 2023)	https://hyporippatlas.npanalysis.org/	LC-MS/MS	Plants and microbes
<i>Databases Emphasizing Secondary Metabolites and Natural Products</i>				
MPOD	(He et al. 2022)	http://medicinalplants.ynau.edu.cn/	LC-MS	Medicinal and food plants
CMAUP	(Zeng et al. 2019)	http://bid2.nus.edu.sg/CMAUP/	LC-MS	Medicinal plants
<i>Meta-Analysis and Data Integration Tools</i>				
MODMS	(Fang et al. 2023)	https://modms.lzu.edu.cn/	LC-MS, RNA-seq	<i>Medicago sativa</i>
PCMD	(Hu et al. 2024)	https://yanglab.hzau.edu.cn/PCMD	LC-MS, GC-MS	Multi-species
The Thing Metabolome Repository family (XMRs)	(Sakurai et al. 2023)	https://metabolites.in/plants/	LC-MS	Multi-species
WikiPathways	(Slenter et al. 2018)	wikipathways.org	Pathway mapping	Multi-species
MDSi	(Li et al. 2023)	http://sky.sxau.edu.cn/MDSi.htm	LC-MS/MS	<i>Setaria italica</i>
PEO	(Koh et al. 2024)	https://expression.plant.tools/	LC-MS	Multi-species

Methodology-based databases

LC-MS/GC-MS centric databases

These databases primarily support high-throughput mass spectrometry workflows (e.g., LC-MS, GC-MS), offering spectral libraries, feature annotation tools and pathway analysis capabilities.

METASPACE-ML

METASPACE-ML (Wadie et al. 2024) is a machine learning-driven approach that addresses this challenge by incorporating novel scores and optimizing False Discovery Rate (FDR) estimation. It surpasses its rule-based predecessor with greater precision, higher throughput and improved detection of low-intensity biologically relevant metabolites. It employs a FDR-controlled method, reporting metabolite ions at a specified confidence level by ranking them against computationally generated decoy ions.

MetFrag

MetFrag (Ruttkies et al. 2016) is an open-source tool for identifying small organic compounds through combinatorial fragmentation. It begins by obtaining candidate structures from databases like PubChem, ChemSpider, or KEGG, or by accepting user-uploaded structure data files. The tool then fragments these candidates using a bond dissociation approach and compares the resulting fragments with product ions in the measured mass spectrum to identify the best-matching compounds.

LIPID MAPS

LIPID Metabolites and Pathways Strategy (LIPID MAPS) (Conroy et al. 2024) is a comprehensive platform for organizing lipid structural and biochemical data. Established 20 years ago, its nomenclature and classification system is widely recognized as the community standard. The platform offers databases for lipid identification, software tools, and educational resources. In 2020, it became an ELIXIR-UK data resource. LIPID MAPS incorporates enhanced metadata, including literature, taxonomic information and improved interoperability, to support FAIR compliance.

LipidSig 2.0

LipidSig (Lin et al. 2021) is the first web-based platform designed for comprehensive lipidomic data analysis. The upgraded LipidSig 2.0 (Liu et al. 2024) enhances efficiency by automating lipid identification, assigning 29 characteristics, and supporting 24 data processing methods. It streamlines key analytical tasks such as data preprocessing, lipid annotation, differential expression,

enrichment, and network analysis, enabling researchers to explore lipid properties and their biological relevance with ease.

LipidSuite

LipidSuite (Mohamed and Hill 2021) is an end-to-end platform for differential lipidomics data analysis, offering a structured workflow for preprocessing, exploration, differential analysis, and enrichment analysis. It supports mwTab (Metabolomics Workbench), Skyline CSV Export, and numerical matrix formats. Users can interactively analyze data, filter subsets by sample type or lipid class, and apply univariate, multivariate, and unsupervised analysis methods.

COCONUT

COLLeCtion of Open NatUral producTs (COCONUT) (Sorokina et al. 2021) is a web-based platform for browsing, searching, and downloading natural products. It offers simple and advanced searches, including structure-based queries and molecular feature searches, with no login required. Users can download datasets in various formats or access data programmatically via a REST API. The platform is Docker-based, allowing easy deployment for local installations and integration into workflows.

PathBank 2.0

Since its first release in 2020, PathBank has become widely popular, with its pathway data integrated into several major omics databases, including Human Metabolome Database (HMDB) (Wishart et al. 2007), DrugBank (Wishart et al. 2008), MarkerDB (Wishart et al. 2021) and MetaboAnalyst (Xia et al. 2009). The recent update, PathBank 2.0 (Wishart et al. 2024), introduces several key improvements, including significant canonical pathways, improved pathway diagrams and descriptions, a focus on drug metabolism and mechanisms, better compatibility for presentations and publications, new tools for pathway filtering and taxonomy and added pathway analysis for enrichment visualization and calculation.

SCIPDb

The Stress Combinations and Their Interactions in Plants Database (SCIPDb) (Priya et al. 2023) provides information on plant responses to various stress combinations, covering morpho-physio-biochemical (phenome) and molecular (transcriptome and metabolome) aspects. SCIPDb serves as a comprehensive informatics hub for plant stress research, facilitating data mining on the phenome, transcriptome, trait-gene ontology, and data-driven studies to advance the understanding of combined stress biology. An analysis of 939 studies found that abiotic-abiotic stress combinations significantly affect crop

yield. SCIPDb integrates metabolome data from six studies across four plant species, with drought and heat stress being the most studied. The database provides a detailed catalog of metabolites with their fold change values.

Multi-Platform Databases (LC–MS, NMR)

MetaboLights

MetaboLights (Yurekten et al. 2024) is a database for metabolomics studies, providing access to raw data and associated metadata for processing and analysis. Established in 2012, MetaboLights (Steinbeck et al. 2012) has undergone recent developments. The latest version features a two-stage process, where data uploaded *via* FTP or Aspera servers is then synchronized to the study directory.

PaintOmics 4

PaintOmics (García-Alcalde et al. 2011) is a web server designed for integrating and visualizing multi-omics data through biological pathway maps. The latest version, PaintOmics 4, (Liu et al. 2022) introduces key enhancements, including support for three pathway databases—KEGG, Reactome, and MapMan—offering broader pathway insights for both animals and plants. Additionally, new metabolite analysis methods address gaps in traditional enrichment approaches. The metabolite hub analysis identifies key compounds influenced by gene expression changes, while the metabolite class activity analysis assesses whether a metabolic class contains more significant elements than expected, indicating experimental regulation.

RefMetaPlant

RefMetaPlant (Shi et al. 2024a) is developed by collecting tissue samples from over 150 plant species representing the five major phyla: *Bryophyta*, *Lycopodiopsida*, *Pteridophyta*, *Gymnospermae* and *Angiospermae*. It integrates an extensive collection of metabolomics data, including a vast number of experimental mass spectra from various plant species, a comprehensive library of biologically relevant compounds sourced from public databases and a large dataset of mass spectra that combines both experimental and *in silico* data. Additionally, it provides a reference metabolome for a diverse range of plant species in ‘msr’ and ‘mgf’ formats, serving as a valuable resource for plant metabolomics research.

OmicsSuite

OmicsSuite (Miao et al. 2023) offers comprehensive, step-by-step workflows tailored for multi-omics applications, making it ideal for horticultural plant breeding and molecular mechanism studies. This tool empowers researchers to deeply explore the molecular data

embedded within complex multi-omics datasets. OmicsSuite can process multi-omics raw data in a variety of formats, including FastA, FastQ, Mutation Annotation Format, mzML, Matrix, and HDF5. The platform prioritizes efficient data transfer and robust pipeline analysis functions. It enables users to create pre-publication-quality images and tables, allowing them to focus on deriving meaningful biological insights.

ModelSEED

ModelSEED (Seaver et al. 2021) is a key resource for draft genome-scale metabolic model construction based on microbial and plant genomes. Its newly released biochemistry database serves as the foundation for ModelSEED and KBase, distinguishing itself through compartmentalization, transport reactions, charge balancing, and proton balancing. It is community-extensible via GitHub and functions as a biochemical ‘Rosetta Stone’, integrating annotations from multiple tools and databases. Built from diverse chemical datasets, it applies standard transformations, redundancy filtering, and thermodynamic calculations for accuracy and consistency.

Species-specific and crop-focused databases

Horticultural crop-specific databases

TOMATOMET

TOMATOMET (Ara et al. 2021) was developed after analysing the compounds in the ripe fruit of 25 different tomato cultivars using liquid chromatography-Orbitrap MS to measure their exact masses. The data was then carefully selected and refined to create the TOMATONET metabolome database, which compiles a vast collection of chemical peaks. Among these, a significant portion of ion peaks was organized into recognized chemical families. The database allows searching peaks by their exact mass values, along with related information such as compound annotations, category classifications, distribution across cultivars, cross-species specificity, retention times, MS/MS spectra, and adduct ion types.

PMhub 1.0

The Plant Metabolome Hub (PMhub 1.0) (Tian et al. 2024) provides comprehensive data on plant metabolites, including reference spectra, genetic foundations, chemical reactions, metabolic pathways and biological functions. It contains extensive information on a vast number of metabolites and high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry spectra, both standard and *in silico*. In addition to literature-based data, PMhub incorporates a large collection of detected features from multiple plant species, with a significant portion successfully annotated using high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry data. This source is further enriched by reference metabolites

features, making it valuable tool for plant metabolomics research.

MMHub

MMHub (version 1.0) (Li et al. 2020) is the first open public database of mass spectra for small chemical compounds in mulberry leaves. It includes electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry (ESI-MS/MS) data from various mulberry resources, collected under independent experimental conditions. The database identifies and annotates numerous metabolites, providing details on their chemical structures. Additional information, such as PubChem data, molecular formulas, and metabolite classifications, is also available. MMHub is a valuable resource for researchers studying mulberry metabolomics, supporting the screening of quality resources and specific metabolites.

ArecaceaeMDB

The Arecaceae Multi-Omics Database (ArecaceaeMDB) (Yang et al. 2023a) provides comprehensive genomic and multi-omics data for the Arecaceae family. It includes genome sequences from seven accessions across six species, resequencing data from 1631 accessions, and 866 spatiotemporal transcriptome datasets. Additionally, 138 spatiotemporal metabolome datasets have been generated using LC-MS-based metabolic profiling. To enhance usability, ArecaceaeMDB offers 12 commonly used online tools, including Sequence Fetch, BLAST, SynVisio, and Enrichment Analysis.

LettuceGDB

LettuceGDB (Guo et al. 2023) is a comprehensive omics data hub for lettuce research, integrating genomic, transcriptomic, metabolomic, and phenotypic data alongside a collected research archive. It offers five core functions and eight built-in tools for genome browsing, gene analysis, and data exploration. With its extensive resources and analytical capabilities, LettuceGDB is a valuable platform for functional genomics and lettuce breeding.

BoGDB

Brassica oleracea Genome Database (BoGDB) (Wang et al. 2022) is the first cross-omics platform for *B. oleracea*, integrating genome, transcriptome, and metabolome data to support genetic research and molecular breeding. It features multiple functional modules, including gene search, heatmaps, genome browsing, and metabolic analysis, within a user-friendly interface. The database will continue expanding with new genomic data to enhance its resources.

BnIR

BnIR (Yang et al. 2023b) is a comprehensive multi-omics database for rapeseed (*Brassica napus*), integrating six omics datasets: genomics, transcriptomics, variomics, epigenetics, phenomics, and metabolomics. It provides numerous “variation–gene expression–phenotype” associations using multiple statistical methods. The platform includes advanced search and analysis tools to enhance data exploration. Case studies demonstrate its effectiveness in identifying candidate genes linked to specific traits and uncovering their regulatory mechanisms.

PlantMetSuite

PlantMetSuite (Liu et al. 2023) is a web-based platform for plant metabolomics analysis, offering interactive bioinformatics tools and databases for seamless multi-omics research. It requires no installation or programming skills, is freely accessible, and will be regularly updated with new libraries and methods. Designed for ease of use, PlantMetSuite empowers researchers to explore and interpret plant metabolomics data effectively.

Coriander genomics database

It is a combined genomic, transcriptomic and metabolic database for coriander (Song et al. 2020) which alongside carrot is a model for studying the evolution of the Apiaceae family. Whilst this is mainly focused on genomic and transcriptomic analyses it does contain metabolomic data which can be searched and compared with the more extensive nucleic acid-based data.

Metabolite database for root, tuber and banana crops

The database by Price et al. (2020) is an exemplary compound database and concentration range for metabolites detected in the major RTB (root, tuber and banana) crops: banana (*Musa spp.*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*), sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*), and yam (*Dioscorea spp.*), following metabolomics-based diversity screening of global collections held within the CGIAR institutes. The dataset including 711 chemical features provides a valuable resource regarding the comparative biochemical composition of each crop highlight diversity available for incorporation into crop improvement programs. Particularly, the tropical crops cassava, sweet potato and banana displayed more complex compositional metabolite profiles with representations of up to 22 chemical classes (unknowns excluded) than that of potato (which was itself originally a tropical species), for which only metabolites from only ten chemical classes were detected.

Broad-spectrum plant metabolomics databases

Plant reactome knowledgebase

Plant Reactome (Gupta et al. 2024) is a free, comprehensive plant pathway knowledge base. It features curated rice reference pathways and gene-orthology-based projections for 129 plant species, covering diverse taxa from single-cell photoautotrophs to higher plants. With 339 reference pathways, it encompasses metabolism, transport, hormone signaling, developmental regulation, and plant responses to environmental stimuli. Beyond a repository, Plant Reactome functions as an interactive platform for analyzing and visualizing omics data, including gene expression, interactions, proteomics, and metabolomics, within a rich biological context.

PMN 16

The Plant Metabolic Network (PMN) (Hawkins et al. 2025) is a free online database on plant metabolism. The latest release includes a vast collection of metabolic pathways, enzymes, metabolites, biochemical reactions, and citations from a wide range of plant and green algal genomes. It also features PlantCyc, a comprehensive pan-plant reference database. This update expands on previous versions by incorporating additional genomes, including species from the African Orphan Crop Consortium and nonflowering plants.

MetaCyc

MetaCyc (Caspi et al. 2020) is a comprehensive, evidence-based database of metabolic pathways and enzymes across all life domains. It includes around 3000 pathways compiled from over 60,000 publications, making it the largest collection of its kind. MetaCyc serves as a key reference for metabolism and is used to generate organism-specific Pathway/Genome Database (PGDBs) (Karp et al. 2019) available on BioCyc.org. It supports various fields, including genome annotation, biochemistry, enzymology, metabolomics and metabolic engineering.

CropMetabolome

The CropMetabolome (Shi et al. 2024b) database is dedicated to constructing crop reference metabolomes and serving as a comprehensive repository for crop metabolomic data. It facilitates the storage, sharing and analysis of metabolic data while providing advanced analytical tools. Covering over 50 crops across eight categories, the database integrates both self-generated and publicly available mass spectral data (using LC-MS/MS platform). Notably, it establishes a reference metabolome for 59 crop species, similar to the reference genome in genomics, enhancing metabolomic research and applications. The annotated metabolites were classified into 12

groups, including alkaloids, flavonoids, lipids and terpenoids. Metadata is provided in the reference metabolome file (.msr' format). This resource serves as a vital reference for metabolic and physiological studies in crops.

Metadb

MetaDb (Gao et al. 2024) is a comprehensive database providing publicly available data on medicinal plant genes, transcription factors, metabolic pathways, and metabolites. It serves as a valuable resource for studying natural product synthesis and metabolic regulation in plants. Additionally, MetaDb offers access to bioinformatics tools such as ChemDoole 2D, BLAST, and SWISS-MODEL, aiding researchers in deeper data analysis and interpretation.

HypoRiPPAtlas

HypoRiPPAtlas (Lee et al. 2023) is a ready-to-use atlas of hypothetical natural product structures for in silico tandem mass spectra searches. It is built using seq2ripp, a machine-learning tool that predicts ribosomally synthesized and post-translationally modified peptides (RiPPs) from genomic data. The atlas identifies RiPPs in microbes and plants and can be expanded to other natural product classes by incorporating additional biosynthetic logic. This resource enables large-scale exploration of biosynthetic pathways and chemical structures of RiPPs.

Databases emphasizing secondary metabolites and natural products

MPOD

MPOD (He et al. 2022) is a database compiling genomes and transcriptomes of medicinal plants along with newly sequenced data from six genomes, 28 transcriptomes, and five metabolomes. It enables orthologous gene queries, homology comparisons, and correlation analyses between metabolite distribution and gene expression. MPOD provides detailed insights into flavonoid, alkaloid, and terpenoid metabolic pathways. Additionally, it includes a "biosynthetic tools" module with bioinformatics tools like SynVisio, heatmap, and enrichment analysis to support synthetic biology research.

CMAUP

The Collective Molecular Activities of Useful Plants (CMAUP) (Zeng et al. 2019) provides a comprehensive molecular overview of a vast range of plant species, including medicinal, food, edible, agricultural, and garden plants traditionally used across numerous countries and regions. It integrates various target classes and activity levels, visually represented in a two-dimensional target-ingredient heatmap. Additionally, CMAUP illustrates

the regulatory effects of these plants on gene ontologies, biological pathways, and diseases.

Meta-analysis and data integration tools

MODMS

The multi-omics database of *Medicago sativa* (alfalfa) (MODMS) (Fang et al. 2023) database is a platform dedicated to alfalfa, designed to include seven key components: genomics, transcriptomics, variations, proteomics, metabolomics and guide RNA (gRNA) tools. The metabolomics module contains 13 metabolomics datasets and researchers could identify differential metabolites under various conditions by inputting treatment details and the names of alfalfa varieties.

PCMD

Plant Comparative Metabolome Database (PCMD) (Hu et al. 2024) is a comprehensive platform for comparing metabolic profiles across 530 plant species. It enables users to analyze species, metabolites, pathways and taxonomy through various online tools, including species comparison, metabolite enrichment and ID conversion. As the most comprehensive plant metabolomics database in terms of species coverage, it offers valuable insights into plant metabolic diversity.

The thing metabolome repository family (XMRs)

The Metabolome Repository Family Database (Sakurai et al. 2023) encompasses food, plant, and other metabolome repositories, allowing researchers to examine sample-specific localization of unknown compounds detected via LC–MS across diverse samples. This resource aids in identifying and prioritizing unknown metabolites. A set of application programming interfaces for XMRs streamlines access to metabolome data, supporting large-scale analysis and data mining. Additionally, various applications, such as integrated metabolome and genome analyses, are showcased.

WikiPathways

WikiPathways (Slenter et al. 2018) is a reliable and comprehensive pathway database. Initially focused on genes and proteins, it previously had limited metabolite annotations. Recent efforts have enhanced metabolic pathway data by mapping metabolites to database identifiers and enriching interaction details, doubling the number of annotated metabolite nodes. Additionally, OpenAPI documentation for web services and FAIR-compliant resource annotations have been introduced to improve compatibility with experimental omics data.

MDSi

Multi-omics database for *Setaria italica* (MDSi) (Li et al. 2023) is a database containing the xiaomi genome, including protein-coding genes and their expression data across various tissues from xiaomi and JG21 samples, visualized through xEFP in-situ. It also provides whole-genome resequencing (WGS) data for foxtail millets and green foxtails, along with corresponding metabolic data. Users can explore SNPs and Indels interactively and access bioinformatics tools such as BLAST, GBrowse, JBrowse, and map viewer for analysis.

PEO

Plant Expression Omnibus (PEO) (Koh et al. 2024) is a web application that provides gene expression insights across a wide range of plant species. It allows users to explore gene expression patterns in different organs, identify organ-specific genes, and discover co-expressed genes. Functional annotations are included to help uncover genetic modules and pathways, supporting comparative kingdom-wide gene expression analysis as well as the discovery of metabolic and developmental pathways. Case studies demonstrate its effectiveness in identifying genes involved in pollen coat biosynthesis in *Arabidopsis* and capsaicin biosynthesis in *Capsicum annuum*. The database is freely accessible.

Bioinformatics tools for metabolomics analysis

The plant metabolomics data sets are analyzed and interpreted with the involvement of a series of computational and bioinformatic steps. As the first step the acquired mass spectra are subsequently compared with the spectral reference databases or libraries, such as METLIN (Montenegro-Burke et al. 2020), KEGG (Kanehisa and Goto 2000) and CropMetabolome (Shi et al. 2024b), to identify the related metabolites. Accurate mass and fragmentation measurements, combined with informative data, are obtained using various software tools for metabolite annotation, including R packages such as CAMERA (Kuhl et al. 2012), RAMclust (Broeckling et al. 2014), xMSannotator (Uppal et al. 2017) and MetAssign (Daly et al. 2014). These tools use parameters like retention time, m/z values, isotopic patterns and adducts to enhance annotation accuracy. Metabolites are subsequently quantified by comparing the intensity of specific, medium or low molecular weight metabolites across various treatment groups or between different sample types. Individual metabolites are integrated into metabolic pathways and networks in plant populations in order to reveal potential metabolic relations and regulatory interactions. Various statistical analysis methods are employed to identify hidden features, detect trends and

distinguish metabolites within plant metabolomes. Lastly integrating the obtained metabolomics data with genomics, transcriptomics and proteomics provides insights into the interactions between distinct molecular layers of plant biology.

Metabolomics peak analysis computational tool (MPACT) (Samples et al. 2023) is an open-source Python package that helps researchers correct mispicked peaks, adjust inter-sample abundance variation across technical replicates, account for in-source ion fragmentation, and eliminate background noise using data from solvent and/or media blanks. Besides, MPACTR (Mason et al. 2025) is also an open-source R package that brings MPACT's functionality to the R ecosystem, allowing users to process and integrate data in a way that aligns with their research needs. Furthermore, the MS1-retention time (MS-RT) (Wang et al. 2025) method evaluates MS/MS clustering in metabolomics. To assess MS-RT method against traditional benchmarking, authors utilized two public datasets. Additionally, MetMiner (Wang et al. 2024) is an R Shiny-based platform for plant metabolomics, enabling large-scale data processing with transparency and reproducibility. It integrates a plant-specific MS database, MDAToolkits for analysis, and a biomarker screening strategy. Validated in case studies, MetMiner is a robust, user-friendly tool for metabolomics research.

Novel tools such as Nextflow4MS-DIAL (Du et al. 2025) are a reproducible workflow for LC-MS metabolomics data processing, validated with MetaboLights (Haug et al. 2020) data. It automates data handling to reduce human errors, supports software containerization for enhanced reproducibility, and facilitates collaborative research. Designed for Unix-like systems, it offers flexibility with compatibility across multiple job schedulers. On the other hand, feature-based molecular networking (FBMN) (Pakkir et al. 2025) is widely used in LC-MS/MS-based non-targeted metabolomics, but downstream data analysis remains a challenge, especially for users unfamiliar with statistical methods. This guide addresses these challenges by detailing data cleanup, normalization, and statistical analysis of FBMN results. It provides step-by-step explanations and code in R, Python, and QIIME2 for streamlined data processing and interpretation.

Computational approaches for metabolite annotation

Metabolite annotation remains a major bottleneck in metabolomics studies due to the complexity of metabolite structures, the vast chemical diversity and the limited availability of comprehensive spectral databases. Advances in high-resolution, accurate mass spectrometry combined with chromatographic separation have transformed high-throughput analysis, enabling the detection

of a broader range of metabolites with increasingly lower detection limits.

MS-based metabolomics offers advantages including lower cost, higher sensitivity, high throughput, and compatibility with chromatography while also providing valuable structural information. Among computational methods, MS/MS spectral database searches have emerged as the gold standard for metabolite annotation, enabling the identification of compounds through their fragmentation patterns (Vinaixa et al. 2016). However, challenges persist due to insufficient metabolite annotation and the limited availability of chemical reference standards, which hinder the biological interpretation of metabolomics data. In this vein the software MetExtractII presents a suite of programs for stable isotope-assisted untargeted metabolomics (Bueschl et al. 2017). This toolbox consists of three complementary modules: M1 (AllExtract) uses mixtures of uniformly highly isotope-enriched and native biological samples for selective detection of the accessible metabolome. M2 (TracExtract) is rather suited to probe the metabolism of endogenous or exogenous secondary metabolites and facilitates the untargeted screening of tracer derivatives from concurrently metabolized native and uniformly labeled tracer substances. Finally, in M3 (FragExtract), tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) fragments of corresponding native and uniformly labeled ions are evaluated and automatically assigned with putative sum formulas. When utilized together these features can greatly improve annotation accuracy.

In the past five years, significant advances have been made in computational metabolite annotation, driven by machine learning (ML), deep learning and improved LC-MS-based workflows. Recent advancements in LC-MS-based metabolic profiling have enhanced data acquisition and processing through the development of dedicated peak-picking and analysis tools. Early tools such as XCMS Online (Tautenhahn et al. 2012), MZmine (Katajamaa and Orešič 2005), MS-DIAL (Tsugawa et al. 2015), MetAlign (De Vos et al. 2007) and xcms (Smith et al. 2006) laid the foundation for automated data processing, peak detection and metabolite annotation. Building on this, newer deep learning frameworks SIRIUS4 (Dührkop et al. 2019) which integrates CSI:FingerID into its architecture have significantly improved structural elucidation by combining fragmentation trees with retention time and ion mobility data. Tools like MS2Query (de Jonge et al. 2023) and DeepMass:Prism (Tiwary et al. 2019) have enabled more precise spectral matching and in silico prediction of fragmentation patterns, expanding the range of detectable metabolites beyond reference libraries. Additionally, CANOPUS (Dührkop et al. 2021) provides valuable structural insights through chemical

class predictions, even when exact metabolites identification is unfeasible.

Retention time prediction tools like RT-Transformer (Xue et al. 2024) and PredRet 2.0 (Low et al. 2021) facilitate cross-platform chromatographic alignment, further boosting annotation reliability. In plant science supervised learning methods such as support vector machines (SVM), random forests (RF), artificial neural networks (ANN), Bayesian models and regression models like LASSO, ridge regression have become standard (MacNish et al. 2025). Unsupervised methods like K-means and principal component analysis (PCA) (Ma et al. 2014) are commonly applied for sample classification and dimensionality reduction while semi-supervised learning methods blend both approaches to handle complex datasets effectively (van Dijk et al. 2020).

Machine learning tools such as MetaClean (Chetnik et al. 2020), PeakOnly (Melnikov et al. 2020) and Peak-Detective (Stancliffe and Patti 2023) have improved data quality by filtering noise and distinguishing true peaks from artifacts using a combination of unsupervised autoencoders and classifiers. Meanwhile, automRm (Eilertz et al. 2022) automates the preprocessing of LC–MS data in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) modes, adapting to complex analytical methods like HILIC. mzRAPP (El Abiead et al. 2022) facilitates the creating and evaluation of benchmark peak lists, helping to detect and correct errors in feature tables. Similarly, RT-Pred (Zakir et al. 2025) predicts retention times across chromatographic systems and allows researchers to train custom models based on their own data for higher accuracy.

Finally, the integration of multi-omics data with enhanced metabolic network modelling platforms such as KBase (Arkin et al. 2018) has significantly enhanced the prediction of novel metabolic functions, offering systems-level and holistic approach to plant metabolite annotation.

Addressing challenges and exploring future trends

The increasing availability of web-based metabolomics resources presents challenges in data integration due to variations in experimental protocols, file formats, and data annotation methods. Standardizing metadata, file structures, and reporting guidelines is crucial for ensuring interoperability across databases. Efforts such as the Metabolomics Standards Initiative (Fiehn et al. 2007) and FAIR principles are essential in addressing these challenges and improving data consistency in horticultural crop research.

ML offers transformative solutions for metabolomics by improving data processing, feature selection, and metabolite identification. Advanced ML algorithms, such as deep learning and ensemble methods, can enhance

noise reduction, detect hidden patterns, and automate feature extraction, reducing the reliance on manual curation. While sophisticated bioinformatics tools are available for metabolomics data analysis, many remain complex and require programming expertise. The development of user-friendly, ML-powered web platforms with intuitive graphical interfaces can bridge this gap by enabling automated data pre-processing, peak detection, and annotation without extensive computational knowledge. Additionally, cloud-based solutions and ML-driven automation tools can enhance accessibility by reducing the dependence on high-performance local computing resources.

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Authors' contributions

ARF conceptualized the manuscript. EK, MB and ARF wrote and edited the manuscript.

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Data availability

Not applicable.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

All authors approved.

Competing interests

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References

- Afendi FM, Okada T, Yamazaki M, Hirai-Morita A, Nakamura Y, Nakamura K, et al. KNApSACK family databases: integrated metabolite–plant species databases for multifaceted plant research. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 2012;53:e1. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pcp/pcr165>.
- Aharoni A, Goodacre R, Fernie AR. Plant and microbial sciences as key drivers in the development of metabolomics research. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2023;120:e2217383120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2217383120>.
- Aiseekh S, Scossa F, Wen W, Luo J, Yan J, Beleggia R, et al. Domestication of crop metabolomes: desired and unintended consequences. *Trends Plant Sci.* 2021;26:650–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2021.02.005>.
- Ara T, Sakurai N, Takahashi S, Waki N, Suganuma H, Aizawa K, et al. TOMATO-MET: A metabolome database consists of 7118 accurate mass values detected in mature fruits of 25 tomato cultivars. 2021;5:e00318. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pld3.318>.
- Arkin AP, Cottingham RW, Henry CS, Harris NL, Stevens RL, Maslov S, et al. KBase: the united states department of energy systems biology

- knowledgebase. *Nat Biotechnol.* 2018;36:566–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.4163>.
- Beleggia R, Rau D, Laidò G, Platani C, Nigro F, Fragasso M, et al. Evolutionary metabolomics reveals domestication-associated changes in tetraploid wheat kernels. *Mol Biol Evol.* 2016;33:1740–53. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msw050>.
- Broeckling CD, Afsar FA, Neumann S, Ben-Hur A, Prenni JE. RAMClust: a novel feature clustering method enables spectral-matching-based annotation for metabolomics data. *Anal Chem.* 2014;86:6812–7. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac501530d>.
- Bueschl C, Kluger B, Neumann NKN, Doppler M, Maschietto V, Thallinger GG, et al. MetExtract II: a software suite for stable isotope-assisted untargeted metabolomics. *Anal Chem.* 2017;89:9518–26. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.7b02518>.
- Caspi R, Billington R, Keseler IM, Kothari A, Krummenacker M, Midford PE, et al. The MetaCyc database of metabolic pathways and enzymes - a 2019 update. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2020;48:D445–53. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz862>.
- Chetnik K, Petrick L, Pandey G. MetaClean: a machine learning-based classifier for reduced false positive peak detection in untargeted LC–MS metabolomics data. *Metabolomics.* 2020;16:117. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11306-020-01738-3>.
- Conroy MJ, Andrews RM, Andrews S, Cockayne L, Dennis EA, Fahy E, et al. LIPID MAPS: update to databases and tools for the lipidomics community. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2024;52:D1677–82. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad896>.
- Daly R, Rogers S, Wandy J, Jankevics A, Burgess KE, Breitling R. MetAssign: probabilistic annotation of metabolites from LC–MS data using a Bayesian clustering approach. *Bioinformatics.* 2014;30:2764–71. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu370>.
- Davey MP, Burrell MM, Woodward FI, Quick WP. Population-specific metabolic phenotypes of *Arabidopsis lyrata* ssp. *petraea*. *New Phytol.* 2008;177:380–8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2007.02282.x>
- de Jonge NF, Louwen JJR, Chekmeneva E, Camuzeaux S, Vermeir FJ, Jansen RS, et al. MS2Query: reliable and scalable MS2 mass spectra-based analogue search. *Nat Commun.* 2023;14:1752. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-37446-4>.
- De Vos RC, Moco S, Lommen A, Keurentjes JJ, Bino RJ, Hall RD. Untargeted large-scale plant metabolomics using liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry. *Nat Protoc.* 2007;2:778–91. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2007.95>.
- van Dijk ADJ, Kootstra G, Kruijer W, de Ridder D. Machine learning in plant science and plant breeding. *iScience.* 2020;24:101890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101890>
- Du X, Dobrowolski A, Brochhausen M, Garrett TJ, Hogan WR, Lemas DJ. Nextflow4MS-DIAL: a reproducible nextflow-based workflow for liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry metabolomics data processing. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom.* 2025;36:433–8. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.4c00364>.
- Dührkop K, Fleischauer M, Ludwig M, Aksenov AA, Melnik AV, Meusel M, et al. SIRIUS 4: a rapid tool for turning tandem mass spectra into metabolite structure information. *Nat Methods.* 2019;16:299–302. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0344-8>.
- Dührkop K, Nothias LF, Fleischauer M, Reher R, Ludwig M, Hoffmann MA, et al. Systematic classification of unknown metabolites using high-resolution fragmentation mass spectra. *Nat Biotechnol.* 2021;39:462–71. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-020-0740-8>.
- Eilertz D, Mitterer M, Buescher JM. automRm: an R package for fully automatic LC–QQQ–MS data preprocessing powered by machine learning. *Anal Chem.* 2022;94:6163–71. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c05224>.
- El Abiead Y, Milford M, Schoeny H, Rusz M, Salek RM, Koellensperger G. Power of mzRAPP-based performance assessments in MS1-based nontargeted feature detection. *Anal Chem.* 2022;94:8588–95. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c05270>.
- Fang L, Liu T, Li M, Dong X, Han Y, Xu C, et al. MODMS: a multi-omics database for facilitating biological studies on alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.). *Hortic Res.* 2023;11:uhad245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hr/uhad245>.
- Fernie AR, Schauer N. Metabolomics-assisted breeding: a viable option for crop improvement? *Trends Genet.* 2009;25:39–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2008.10.010>.
- Fernie AR, Stitt M. On the discordance of metabolomics with proteomics and transcriptomics: coping with increasing complexity in logic, chemistry, and network interactions scientific correspondence. *Plant Physiol.* 2012;158:1139–45. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.112.193235>.
- Fiehn O, Robertson D, Griffin J, van der Werf M, Nikolau B, Morrison N, et al. The metabolomics standards initiative (MSI). *Metabolomics.* 2007;3:175–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11306-007-0070-6>.
- Fiehn O, Kopka J, Dörmann P, Altmann T, Trethewey RN, Willmitzer L. Metabolite profiling for plant functional genomics. *Nat Biotechnol.* 2000;18:1157–61. <https://doi.org/10.1038/81137>.
- Gao Q, Zhang J, Cao J, Xiang C, Yuan C, Li X, et al. MetaDb: a database for metabolites and their regulation in plants with an emphasis on medicinal plants. *Mol Hort.* 2024;4:17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43897-024-00095-2>.
- García-Alcalde F, García-López F, Dopazo J, Conesa A. Paintomics: a web based tool for the joint visualization of transcriptomics and metabolomics data. *Bioinformatics.* 2011;27:137–9. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq594>.
- Giera M, Yanes O, Siuzdak G. Metabolite discovery: biochemistry's scientific driver. *Cell Metab.* 2022;34:21–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2021.11.005>.
- Guo Z, Li B, Du J, Shen F, Zhao Y, Deng Y, et al. LettuceGDB: the community database for lettuce genetics and omics. *Plant Commun.* 2023;4:100425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xplc.2022.100425>.
- Gupta P, Elser J, Hooks E, D'Eustachio P, Jaiswal P, Naithani S. Plant Reactome Knowledgebase: empowering plant pathway exploration and OMICS data analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2024;52:D1538–47. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1052>.
- Haug K, Cochrane K, Nainala VC, Williams M, Chang J, Jayaseelan KV, et al. MetaboLights: a resource evolving in response to the needs of its scientific community. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2020;48:D440–4. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz1019>.
- Hawkins C, Xue B, Yasmin F, Wyatt G, Zerbe P, Rhee SY. Plant metabolic network 16: expansion of underrepresented plant groups and experimentally supported enzyme data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2025;53:D1606–13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae991>.
- He S, Yang L, Ye S, Lin Y, Li X, Wang Y, et al. MPOD: applications of integrated multi-omics database for medicinal plants. *Plant Biotechnol J.* 2022;20:797–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.13769>.
- Hu Y, Ruan Y, Zhao XL, Jiang F, Liu D, Zhu Q, et al. PCMD: A multilevel comparison database of intra- and cross-species metabolic profiling in 530 plant species. *Plant Commun.* 2024;5: 101038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xplc.2024.101038>.
- Kanehisa M, Goto S. KEGG: Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes. *Nucleic Acids Research.* 2000;28(1):27–30. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/28.1.27>.
- Karp PD, Billington R, Caspi R, Fulcher CA, Latendresse M, Kothari A, Keseler IM, Krummenacker M, Midford PE, Ong Q, Ong WK, Paley SM, Subhraveti P. The BioCyc collection of microbial genomes and metabolic pathways. *Briefings in Bioinformatics.* 2019;20(4):1085–93. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbx085>.
- Katajamaa M, Oresic M. Processing Methods for Differential Analysis of LC/MS Profile Data. 2005;6:179. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-6-179>.
- Kliebenstein D. Advancing genetic theory and application by metabolic quantitative trait loci analysis. *Plant Cell.* 2009;21:1637–46. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.109.067611>.
- Koh E, Goh W, Julca I, Villanueva E, Mutwil M. PEO: plant expression omnibus – a comparative transcriptomic database for 103 Archaeplastida. *Plant J.* 2024;117:1592–603. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16566>.
- Kuhl C, Tautenhahn R, Böttcher C, Larson TR, Neumann S. CAMERA: an integrated strategy for compound spectra extraction and annotation of liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry data sets. 2012;84:283–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac202450g>.
- Lee YY, Guler M, Chigumba DN, Wang S, Mittal N, Miller C, et al. HypoRiPPAtlas as an atlas of hypothetical natural products for mass spectrometry database search. *Nat Commun.* 2023;14:4219. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39905-4>.
- Li X, Hou S, Feng M, Xia R, Li J, Tang S, Han Y, et al. MDSi: multi-omics database for *setaria italica*. *BMC Plant Biol.* 2023;23:223. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12870-023-04238-3>.

- Li D, Ma B, Xu X, Chen G, Li T, He N. MMHub, a database for the mulberry metabolome. Database (Oxford). 2020;2020:baaa011. <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baaa011>.
- Lin WJ, Shen PC, Liu HC, Cho YC, Hsu MK, Lin IC, et al. LipidSig: a web-based tool for lipidomic data analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2021;49:W336–45. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab419>
- Liu Y, Liu HZ, Chen DK, Zeng HY, Chen YL, Yao N. PlantMetSuite: a user-friendly web-based tool for metabolomics analysis and visualisation. *Plants (Basel).* 2023;12:2880. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12152880>.
- Liu T, Salguero P, Petek M, Martinez-Mira C, Balzano-Nogueira L, Ramšak Ž, et al. PaintOmics 4: new tools for the integrative analysis of multi-omics datasets supported by multiple pathway databases. 2022;50:W551–9. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac352>.
- Liu CH, Shen PC, Lin WJ, Liu HC, Tsai MH, Huang TY, et al. LipidSig 2.0: integrating lipid characteristic insights into advanced lipidomics data analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2024;52:W390–7. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae335>.
- Low DY, Micheau P, Koistinen VM, Hanhineva K, Abrankó L, Rodriguez-Mateos A, et al. Data sharing in predRet for accurate prediction of retention time: application to plant food bioactive compounds. *Food Chem.* 2021;357: 129757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.129757>.
- Ma C, Zhang HH, Wang X. Machine learning for big data analytics in plants. *Trends Plant Sci.* 2014;19:798–808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2014.08.004>.
- MacNish TR, Danilevicz MF, Bayer PE, Bestry MS, Edwards D. Application of machine learning and genomics for orphan crop improvement. *Nat Commun.* 2025;16:982. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-56330-x>.
- Mason AR, Johnson G Jr, Krampen J, Nguyen JNT, Balunas MJ, Schloss PD. mpactR: an R adaptation of the metabolomics peak analysis computational tool (MPACT) for use in reproducible data analysis pipelines. *Microbiol Resour Annu.* 2025;114:e0099724. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mra.00997-24>.
- Melnikov AD, Tsentlovich YP, Yanshole VV. Deep learning for the precise peak detection in high-resolution LC–MS data. *Anal Chem.* 2020;92:588–92. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b04811>.
- Meyer RC, Steinfath M, Liseč J, Becher M, Witucka-Wall H, Törjék O, et al. The metabolic signature related to high plant growth rate in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2007;104:4759–64. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0609709104>.
- Miao BB, Dong W, Gu YX, Han ZF, Luo X, Ke CH, et al. OmicsSuite: a customized and pipelined suite for analysis and visualization of multi-omics big data. *Hortic Res.* 2023;10:uhad195. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hr/uhad195>.
- Mohamed A, Hill MM. LipidSuite: interactive web server for lipidomics differential and enrichment analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2021;49:W346–51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab327>.
- Montenegro-Burke JR, Guijas C, Siuzdak G. METLIN: a tandem mass spectral library of standards. In Li S, editors. *Computational Methods and Data Analysis for Metabolomics*. New York: Springer; 2020. p.149–63. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-0239-3_9
- Oliver SG, Winson MK, Kell DB, Baganz F. Systematic Functional Analysis of the Yeast Genome. 1998;16:373–8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-7799\(98\)01214-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-7799(98)01214-1).
- Pakkir Shah AK, Walter A, Ottosson F, Russo F, Navarro-Díaz M, Boldt J, et al. Statistical analysis of feature-based molecular networking results from non-targeted metabolomics data. *Nat Protoc.* 2025;20:92–162. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-024-01046-3>.
- Perez de Souza L, Fernie AR. Computational methods for processing and interpreting mass spectrometry-based metabolomics. *Essays Biochem.* 2024;68:5–13. <https://doi.org/10.1042/EBC20230019>
- Perez de Souza L, Naake T, Tohge T, Fernie AR. From chromatogram to analyte to metabolite. How to pick horses for courses from the massive web resources for mass spectral plant metabolomics. *Gigascience.* 2017;6:1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/gix037>
- Price EJ, Drapal M, Perez-Fons L, Amah D, Bhattacharjee R, Heider B, et al. Metabolite database for root, tuber, and banana crops to facilitate modern breeding in understudied crops. *Plant J.* 2020;101:1258–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.14649>.
- Priya P, Patil M, Pandey P, Singh A, Babu VS, Senthil-Kumar M. Stress combinations and their interactions in plants database: a one-stop resource on combined stress responses in plants. *Plant J.* 2023;116:1097–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16497>.
- Ruttkies C, Schymanski EL, Wolf S, Hollender J, Neumann S. MetFrag relaunched: incorporating strategies beyond *in silico* fragmentation. *J Cheminform.* 2016;8:3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-016-0115-9>.
- Sakurai N, Yamazaki S, Suda K, Hosoki A, Akimoto N, Takahashi H, et al. The thing metabolome repository family (XMRs): comparable untargeted metabolome databases for analyzing sample-specific unknown metabolites. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023;51:D660–77. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1058>.
- Samples RM, Puckett SP, Balunas MJ. Metabolomics peak analysis computational tool (MPACT): an advanced informatics tool for metabolomics and data visualization of molecules from complex biological samples. *Anal Chem.* 2023;95:8770–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.2c04632>.
- Sauter H, Lauer M, Fritsch H. Metabolic profiling of plants. In: Baker DR, Fenyes JG, Moberg WK, editors. *Synthesis and Chemistry of Agrochemicals II*. American Chemical Society; 1991. p.288–99. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bk-1991-0443.ch024>
- Schläpfer P, Zhang P, Wang C, Kim T, Banf M, Chae L, et al. Genome-wide prediction of metabolic enzymes, pathways, and gene clusters in plants. *Plant Physiol.* 2017;173:2041–59. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.16.01942>.
- Seaver SMD, Liu F, Zhang Q, Jeffryes J, Faria JP, Edirisinghe JN, et al. The ModelSEED biochemistry database for the integration of metabolic annotations and the reconstruction, comparison and analysis of metabolic models for plants, fungi and microbes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2021;49:D1555. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa746>.
- Shen S, Zhan C, Yang C, Fernie AR, Luo J. Metabolomics-centered mining of plant metabolic diversity and function: Past decade and future perspectives. *Mol Plant.* 2023;16:43–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molp.2022.09.007>.
- Shi H, Wu X, Zhu Y, Jiang T, Wang Z, Li X, et al. RefMetaPlant: a reference metabolome database for plants across five major phyla. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2024a;52:D1614–28. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad980>.
- Shi H, Zhu Y, Wu X, Jiang T, Li X, Liu J, et al. CropMetabolome: a comprehensive metabolome database for major crops across eight categories. *Plant J.* 2024b;119:1613–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16858>.
- Slenter DN, Kutmon M, Hanspers K, Riutta A, Windsor J, Nunes N, et al. WikiPathways: a multifaceted pathway database bridging metabolomics to other omics research. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018;46:D661–7. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkx1064>.
- Smith CA, Want EJ, O'Maille G, Abagyan R, Siuzdak G. XCMS: processing mass spectrometry data for metabolite profiling using nonlinear peak alignment, matching, and identification. *Anal Chem.* 2006;78:779–87. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac051437y>
- Song X, Nie F, Chen W, Ma X, Gong K, Yang Q, et al. Coriander Genomics Database: a genomic, transcriptomic, and metabolic database for coriander. *Hortic Res.* 2020;7:55. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41438-020-0261-0>.
- Sorokina M, Merseburger P, Rajan K, Yirik MA, Steinbeck C. COCONUT online: collection of open natural products database. *J Cheminform.* 2021;13:2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-020-00478-9>.
- Stancliffe E, Patti GJ. PeakDetective: a semisupervised deep learning-based approach for peak curation in untargeted metabolomics. *Anal Chem.* 2023;95:9397–403. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.3c00764>.
- Steinbeck C, Conesa P, Haug K, Mahendrakar T, Williams M, Maguire E, et al. MetaboLights: towards a new COSMOS of metabolomics data management. *Metabolomics.* 2012;8:757–60. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11306-012-0462-0>.
- Sulpice R, Pyl ET, Ishihara H, Trenkamp S, Steinfath M, Witucka-Wall H, et al. Starch as a major integrator in the regulation of plant growth. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2009;106:10348–53. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0903478106>.
- Tautenhahn R, Patti GJ, Rinehart D, Siuzdak G. XCMS online: a web-based platform to process untargeted metabolomic data. *Anal Chem.* 2012;84:5035–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac300698c>.
- Theodoridis GA, Gika HG, Want EJ, Wilson ID. Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry based global metabolite profiling: a review. *Anal Chim Acta.* 2012;711:7–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2011.09.042>.
- Tian Z, Hu X, Xu Y, Liu M, Liu H, Li D, et al. PMhub 1.0: a comprehensive plant metabolome database. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2024;52:D1579–87. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad811>.
- Tiwary S, Levy R, Gutenbrunner P, Salinas Soto F, Palaniappan KK, Deming L, et al. High-quality MS/MS spectrum prediction for data-dependent and

- data-independent acquisition data analysis. *Nat Methods*. 2019;16:519–25. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0427-6>.
- Tohge T, Fernie AR. Web-based resources for mass-spectrometry-based metabolomics: a user's guide. *Phytochemistry*. 2009;70:450–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2009.02.004>.
- Tsugawa H, Cajka T, Kind T, Ma Y, Higgins B, Ikeda K, et al. MS-DIAL: data-independent MS/MS deconvolution for comprehensive metabolome analysis. *Nat Methods*. 2015;12:523–6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3393>.
- Uppal K, Walker DI, Jones DP. xMSannotator: an R package for network-based annotation of high-resolution metabolomics data. *Anal Chem*. 2017;89:1063–7. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.6b01214>.
- Vinaixa M, Schymanski EL, Neumann S, Navarro M, Salek RM, Yanes O. Mass spectral databases for LC/MS- and GC/MS-based metabolomics: state of the field and future prospects. *TrAC, Trends Anal Chem*. 2016;78:23–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2015.09.005>.
- Wadie B, Stuart L, Rath CM, Drotleff B, Mamedov S, Alexandrov T. METASPACE-ML: context-specific metabolite annotation for imaging mass spectrometry using machine learning. *Nat Commun*. 2024;15:9110. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-52213-9>.
- Wang Y, Ji J, Fang Z, Yang L, Zhuang M, Zhang Y, et al. BoGDB: an integrative genomic database for *Brassica oleracea* L. *Front Plant Sci*. 2022;13:852291. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.852291>.
- Wang X, Liang S, Yang W, Yu K, Liang F, Zhao B, et al. MetMiner: A user-friendly pipeline for large-scale plant metabolomics data analysis. *J Integr Plant Biol*. 2024;66:2329–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jipb.13774>.
- Wang X, Abiead YE, Acharya DD, Brown CJ, Clevenger K, Hu J, et al. MS-RT: a method for evaluating MS/MS clustering performance for metabolomics data. *J Proteome Res*. 2025;24:1778–90. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.4c00881>.
- Wishart DS, Bartok B, Oler E, Liang KYH, Budinski Z, Berjanskii M, et al. MarkerDB: an online database of molecular biomarkers. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2021;49:D1259–67. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1067>.
- Wishart DS, Knox C, Guo AC, Cheng D, Shrivastava S, Tzur D, et al. DrugBank: a knowledgebase for drugs, drug actions and drug targets. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2008;36:D901–6. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkm958>.
- Wishart DS, Kruger R, Sivakumaran A, Harford K, Sanford S, Doshi R, et al. PathBank 2.0—the pathway database for model organism metabolomics. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2024;52:D654–62. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1041>.
- Wishart DS, Tzur D, Knox C, Eisner R, Guo A, Young N, et al. HMDB: the Human Metabolome Database. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2007;35:D521–D26. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkl923>.
- Xia J, Psychogios N, Young N, Wishart DS. MetaboAnalyst: a web server for metabolomic data analysis and interpretation. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2009;37:W652–60. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp356>.
- Xue J, Wang B, Ji H, Li W. RT-Transformer: retention time prediction for metabolite annotation to assist in metabolite identification. *Bioinformatics*. 2024;40:btac084. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btac084>.
- Yang Z, Liu Z, Xu H, Li Y, Huang S, Cao G, et al. ArecaceaeMDB: a comprehensive multi-omics database for arecaceae breeding and functional genomics studies. *Plant Biotechnol J*. 2023a;21:11–3. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.13945>.
- Yang Z, Wang S, Wei L, Huang Y, Liu D, Jia Y, et al. BnIR: a multi-omics database with various tools for *Brassica napus* research and breeding. *Mol Plant*. 2023b;16:775–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molp.2023.03.007>.
- Yurekten O, Payne T, Tejera N, Amaladoss FX, Martin C, Williams M, et al. MetaboLights: open data repository for metabolomics. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2024;52:D640–6. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1045>.
- Zakir M, LeVatte MA, Wishart DS. RT-Pred: a web server for accurate, customized liquid chromatography retention time prediction of chemicals. *J Chromatogr A*. 2025;1747:465816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2025.465816>.
- Zeng X, Zhang P, Wang Y, Qin C, Chen S, He W, et al. CMAUP: a database of collective molecular activities of useful plants. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2019;47:D1118–27. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky965>.

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